

IMPACT AND DAMAGE RESISTANCE OF SANDWICH BEAMS MADE FROM SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS AT LOW TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the response to low-velocity impact of sustainable and conventional sandwich beams tested at two temperatures: room temperature and -40°C . The sustainable sandwich beams are made by two flax/epoxy skins with a recycled PET foam core, while the conventional beams use glass/epoxy skins and a PVC foam core. Both types of sandwich beams were impacted with energies ranging from 2.5 J to 20 J using a drop-weight tower, and their responses were evaluated in terms of absorbed energy, peak force, energy absorption ratio, and effective flexural modulus. The results indicate that the conventional structure exhibits superior impact performance and lower temperature sensitivity. However, the flax/PET sandwich beam achieved peak loads comparable to the conventional sandwich, with minimal variation due to temperature, and demonstrated efficient energy absorption at low impact energies under cold conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are widely employed in the aerospace, automotive, marine, and rail sectors due to their excellent stiffness-to-weight ratio, high energy absorption capacity, and superior performance under flexural loads. These structures are made of two stiff composite skins and a lightweight core. They offer additional benefits such as thermal and acoustic insulation. Conventional sandwich cores are often made from synthetic materials and include polymeric foams, honeycombs, or corrugated sheets [1].

During operation, sandwich panels may be subjected to accidental low-velocity impacts, such as tool drops during maintenance or debris strikes in high-speed trains. Depending on the impact energy level, these impacts can result in barely visible damage or catastrophic failure. One of the main drawbacks of these structures is their limited impact resistance [1], especially in cases where internal damage may not be externally detectable. Prior studies have extensively characterized the impact behaviour of traditional sandwich structures combining synthetic cores and composite skins [2], though most focus on ambient conditions.

However, in real-world applications such as cryogenic storage, Arctic operations, or aerospace thermal cycling, these structures may be exposed to low temperatures. At these temperatures, core and matrix brittleness typically increases, and mismatched thermal expansion coefficients between skin and core can introduce residual stresses [1], significantly modifying impact response.

Due to growing environmental concerns and the increasing demand for sustainable materials, research has intensified into the development of bio-based sandwich structures. Natural fibres such as flax have emerged as a promising alternative to glass fibres thanks to their relatively high specific strength, low density, and renewable origin [3], [4]. However, there are certain limitations to their use, including high moisture uptake, reduced thermal stability, and a strong dependency of mechanical properties on processing conditions or seasonal variations [5].

Recycled polymeric foams, particularly thermoplastic-based materials, have attracted increasing attention as sustainable core alternatives. Thermoset polymers such as polyurethane or Polymethacrylimide are difficult to recycle, whereas thermoplastics like polyethylene terephthalate (PET) are widely available and industrially recycled. PET foams offer favourable mechanical properties, including high specific strength and stiffness, along with low thermal conductivity [6]. These features, combined with the large volume of post-consumer PET waste, make them an attractive ecological solution for sandwich core applications.

Despite the growing interest in sustainable alternatives, the impact behaviour of these eco-sandwich configurations, particularly at sub-zero temperatures, remains insufficiently explored [1], [7]. Moreover, findings obtained for specific core–skin combinations and geometries cannot be generalized, as their response is highly dependent on structural configuration, stacking sequence, and test conditions.

This study investigates the low-velocity impact behaviour of sandwich beams made from flax/epoxy skins combined with recycled PET foam cores. The performance is compared against a conventional configuration comprising glass/epoxy skins and a PVC foam core. Tests were conducted at both room temperature and -40°C to assess the influence of temperature on structural performance. The analysis focuses on critical mechanical response parameters such as peak impact force, absorbed energy, effective flexural stiffness, and failure mechanisms observed via high-speed imaging. The findings aim to enhance the understanding of sustainable sandwich composites and support their future implementation in structural applications subjected to impact loading.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

A sustainable sandwich structure was analysed and compared to a conventional reference configuration. Both were manufactured with identical stacking sequences and resin systems, but differed in fibre type and core material. The sustainable sandwich was made by two composite skins of a symmetric laminate with four plies of a flax/epoxy woven fabric with a fibre content of 49%, supplied by Simcas Composites (EPC 300-F200T-5043-52-1000). The lay-up sequence used was [0/90]_s. The core was made from a recycled PET foam (ArmaPET GR200, 200 kg/m^3), provided by Composites Quimiber.

The reference sandwich used the same stacking sequence and resin system, but incorporated a glass fibre woven fabric (EPC300-G200T-40-1270) in place of flax. The core of the reference configuration was a PVC foam (Divinycell HP200, 200 kg/m^3), supplied by DIAB.

Rectangular beam specimens with dimensions of 270 mm in length and 50 mm in width were extracted from the manufactured sandwich panels. All specimens featured a core thickness of 10 mm and skin

thicknesses of 1.2 mm. The fabrication process was carried out at the Composite Materials Laboratory of the Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA), in strict adherence to the manufacturing guidelines specified in the technical datasheets of the materials.

2.2 Low velocity impact test

Low-velocity impact tests were performed using a drop-weight impact tower (CEAST Fractovis 6875). The striker had a semicylindrical head of 20 mm in diameter and a total mass of 3.995 kg. A piezoelectric load cell mounted on the striker allowed for the continuous recording of the impact force. The impact velocity was measured using a photoelectric sensor, which also activated a rebound prevention system to ensure single-impact events. The tests were conducted according to ASTM D7136, covering impact energies of 2.5, 5, 7.5, 10, 12.5, 15, 17.5, and 20 J. All configurations were tested at room temperature and at -40°C . At least five specimens were tested per configuration.

From the force-time signal recorded during each impact, the displacement of the striker tip was computed via double integration, using the initial impact velocity as a starting point. Assuming continuous contact between the striker and the specimen, this displacement was taken as representative of the vertical deflection at the mid-span of the beam. The energy transferred to the specimen was calculated as the area under the resulting force-displacement curve. Energy-time plots were constructed accordingly. In tests where no catastrophic failure occurred, the final energy value on the curve was interpreted as the absorbed energy during damage progression. In contrast, for specimens that failed during impact, the maximum value reached was considered as the absorbed energy up to failure, as the curve does not drop afterward (Sánchez et al., 2005).

2.3 Digital image correlation method (DIC)

Each test was recorded using a PHOTRON FASTCAM SA-Z high-speed camera, positioned perpendicular to the front face of the specimen and operating at 30,000 frames per second. The footage was processed using a 2D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique, which enabled the visualization and analysis of the strain fields developed during the impact event. The speckle pattern was designed such that each spot covered approximately 3–5 pixels to ensure high correlation accuracy.

In this study, the DIC method was employed as a verification tool to assess the validity of the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory under low-velocity impact conditions. **Figure 1** presents as an example the strain distribution obtained from a flax/PET sandwich specimen impacted at 12.5 J under room temperature conditions.

Figure 1 (a) show the vertical strain component ϵ_{yy} . The mean strain along the beam length remains close to zero, showing that the transverse deformation is negligible. However, a localized compressive region is clearly observed beneath the impactor (C_0), corresponding to core indentation and local crushing phenomena. In contrast, at a remote location away from the impact zone (P_0), the strain remains negligible, further supporting the assumption of negligible vertical strain in the global response.

Figure 1 (b) represents the longitudinal strain field ϵ_{xx} . Two virtual extensometers were defined: E_0 on the upper skin and E_1 on the lower skin. The results indicate that the top face experiences compressive strains, while the bottom face undergoes tensile strains, consistent with pure bending behaviour. These

observations confirm that the global deformation of the sandwich beam under the studied impact conditions adheres to the assumptions of Euler–Bernoulli beam theory.

Figure 1. (a) Transverse strain distribution and (b) longitudinal strain distribution in the Flax/PET sandwich beam under low-velocity impact at $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Based on these results, the effective Young's modulus of the system was subsequently estimated using the beam bending equation for a 3-point bending configuration:

$$E_{eff} = \frac{L^3}{4bh^3} \left(\frac{F}{\delta} \right) \quad (1)$$

where L is the span length, b the beam width, h the total thickness, F the applied load, and δ the mid-span deflection.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examines the main results obtained from the low-velocity impact tests conducted on the sustainable (Flax/PET) and conventional (Glass/PVC) sandwich beams. The variables analysed include absorbed energy, energy absorption ratio, peak impact force, and equivalent flexural modulus, under two temperature conditions: room temperature ($20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and sub-zero temperature ($-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Additionally, high-speed recordings were used to correlate the failure evolution with the load evolution.

3.1 Energy absorption and energy ratio

Figures 2-3 show the evolution of the absorbed energy and the energy ratio, respectively, as a function of the impact energy for both sandwich configurations at room temperature and $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In all cases, the absorbed energy increases linearly with impact energy up to a threshold, beyond which the curve either plateaus or, in specific configurations, begins to decrease slightly. This behaviour marks a transition from sub-critical damage mechanisms, such as matrix cracking and fibre debonding [8], to more severe failure modes, including core shear, indentation, or partial perforation.

Figure 2. Absorbed energy as a function of impact energy for both sandwich configurations: (a) room temperature and (b) -40°C .

For the Flax/PET sandwich, the absorbed energy increases significantly with impact energy, but shows a sharp rise at 12.5 J under ambient conditions and 10 J at -40°C , indicating a shift in the dominant failure mode. This behaviour is also reflected in the energy ratio, as shown in Figure 3. The Flax/PET system reaches values near unity at the transition energy, indicating that nearly all the impact energy is dissipated through irreversible damage. Beyond this point, the ratio tends to decrease, as the structure is no longer capable of absorbing additional energy, suggesting that the beams are close to complete collapse.

Figure 3. Energy absorption ratio as a function of impact energy for both sandwich configurations: (a) room temperature and (b) -40°C .

Meanwhile, the Glass/PVC configuration displays a more gradual increase in both absorbed energy and energy ratio. No clear transition is observed at room temperature, although the data suggests that the threshold energy lies between 12.5 J and 15 J. Additionally, the influence of temperature on this configuration appears to be limited, as the overall trends between 20°C and -40°C remain relatively similar. This implies that the onset of extensive damage occurs at slightly higher energies compared to the PET configuration, albeit with less efficient energy dissipation.

At higher impact energies (15 J at 20°C and 17.5 J at -40°C), the energy ratio of the Glass/PVC system surpasses that of the Flax/PET sandwich. However, this apparent advantage does not reflect superior energy

absorption performance, but rather the fact that the PVC structure is still resisting and has not yet reached complete failure. By comparison, the PET system has already undergone its full damage progression and begins to lose efficiency as the dominant failure modes saturate. Overall, these results demonstrate that the Flax/PET sandwich exhibits superior energy absorption performance, particularly under moderate impact energies and cold environments, although it is related to a higher level of damage.

3.2 Peak load and failure response

Figure 6 shows the variation of the peak impact force as a function of impact energy. In all cases, the peak load increases with energy until a threshold value is reached, beyond which the growth rate diminishes. This trend reflects the onset of damage mechanisms and the associated reduction in structural stiffness.

Figure 6. Peak impact force as a function of impact energy for both sandwich configurations: (a) room temperature and (b) -40°C .

In the Flax/PET sandwich, the peak load exhibits a similar trend at both temperatures, with nearly identical values across the entire energy range. This indicates that the mechanical properties of the PET foam, namely stiffness and strength, are minimally affected by the temperature reduction.

As shown in **Figure 7**, multiple diagonal cracks initiate just after the point of maximum load, coinciding with a sudden drop in the measured force. This damage sequence is captured in frames A to F, and involves the formation of diagonal shear cracks at approximately 45° within the PET foam core (frame C), followed by their propagation through the core thickness (frame D), and subsequent core-skin debonding beneath the impactor (frames E and F). This damage sequence compromises the structural integrity of the beam and prevents elastic recovery, thereby resulting in full energy absorption without rebound.

Figure 7. Force–time and energy–time curves for PET-core sandwich at 12.5 J and 20°C.

In contrast, the response of the Glass/PVC sandwich differs significantly beyond the threshold energy. As observed in **Figure 6**, temperature has little influence below the threshold, where peak force remains stable. This limited thermal sensitivity aligns with observations by Castellanos et al. [1], who studied PVC-core sandwiches with carbon/vinylester skins under -50°C impacts. However, while those authors reported a decrease in peak force at low temperature, our results show an increase at -40°C once the threshold energy is exceeded. This discrepancy may stem from the lower temperature sensitivity of the glass/epoxy skins used in this work, which are less brittle compared to the carbon/vinylester laminates employed by Castellanos et al. [1]. Additionally, differences in specimen geometry and impact configuration, such as the use of rectangular panels and hemispherical impactors, could further contribute to the different behaviour observed.

At the threshold energy, barely any damage is observed in the PVC core. As shown in **Figure 8**, damage is confined to compressive failure of the upper skin, with no significant visible damage in the core region. This damage pattern begins with localized core crushing (frame C), followed by top skin failure (frame D). The absence of rebound confirms that the residual energy remains trapped within the damaged structure, likely due to plastic collapse and progressive fracture in the core. The force–time curve of the Glass/PVC beam does not exhibit a sharp drop to zero, unlike the Flax/PET sandwich, which is consistent with a more localized and gradual failure mode.

These results indicate that the Glass/PVC sandwich beam sustains higher peak loads and exhibits delayed damage initiation compared to the Flax/PET sandwich.

Figure 8. Force–time and energy–time curves for PVC-core sandwich at 17.5 J and 20°C.

3.3 Effective flexural modulus

Figure 9 shows the evolution of the effective flexural modulus as a function of impact energy, estimated from the linear portion of the force–displacement curve under the assumption of Euler–Bernoulli beam behaviour. The effective modulus remains nearly constant across the studied energy range, indicating that both sandwich systems are relatively insensitive to the associated strain rate. A difference of approximately 10% is observed between the Flax/PET and Glass/PVC configurations.

Figure 9. Effective flexural modulus as a function of impact energy: (a) room temperature and (b) -40°C .

Both materials exhibit a slight increase in stiffness at -40°C compared to room temperature, with gains of approximately 20% for Flax/PET and 15% for Glass/PVC. This suggests a temperature-induced stiffening effect. Interestingly, this trend contrasts with the energy absorption behaviour, where both systems displayed

increased brittleness. These results indicate that, despite a reduction in damage tolerance at low temperatures, the initial elastic response of both configurations improves moderately.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study analysed the low-velocity impact response of two sandwich beam configurations tested at two temperatures. In the energy range and thermal conditions considered, sandwich beams manufactured with natural and sustainable materials exhibited inferior performance compared to conventional sandwich structures composed of glass/epoxy skins and PVC foam cores. This outcome is consistent with the superior mechanical properties of the constituent materials in the reference system. In particular, the Glass/PVC sandwich showed a higher threshold energy, and its impact response remained largely unaffected by temperature variations.

Additionally, the conventional sandwich exhibited a progressive and localized failure mode, whereas the Flax/PET configuration showed a more abrupt and catastrophic failure when subjected to impact energies at or above its threshold. However, in terms of peak impact force, the Flax/PET system demonstrated performance comparable to the reference sandwich, with limited temperature sensitivity. These results suggest that, while sustainable sandwich structures can match the load-bearing capacity of conventional designs, their damage tolerance and energy thresholds are more susceptible to environmental conditions. Therefore, further improvements in core toughness and interfacial strength are required to enhance their impact resistance and make them more competitive in demanding applications.

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